

Pyroxene megacryst in lunar meteorite NWA 14685: constraints on deep-crustal cooling and lower lunar crustal evolution

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Introduction: The currently available samples of the lunar deep crust are extremely scarce, thus there is still a lack of direct constraints on the rock composition, chemical composition and thermal evolution history of the lower crust of the moon [1]. Lunar meteorites provide an important complement to returned samples because they sample regions beyond the Apollo, Luna, and recent Chang'e sampling sites. Here we investigate a ~4 mm pyroxene megacryst in the feldspathic fragmental breccia NWA 14685 to constrain its cooling history, burial depth, and implications for lower lunar crustal evolution (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1 A. backscattered electron (BSE) image of the pyroxene megacryst, with Line-1 and Line-2 indicating the positions of the two electron probe microanalysis (EPMA) profiles. Panels b to d are elemental maps of the pyroxene megacryst obtained by energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDS) mapping.

Methods and Results: The pyroxene megacryst was characterized by backscattered-electron imaging, EDS mapping, EBSD, and EPMA line profiles. Element maps show that Mg- and Fe-enriched bands spatially coincide and are anticorrelated with Ca-rich domains, indicating a well-developed exsolution texture.

Fig. 2 Major-element compositional profiles across the pyroxene megacryst, showing a low-Ca orthopyroxene host,

high-Ca clinopyroxene exsolved lamellae, and an intermediate transitional zone.

EPMA profiles reveal three compositional domains: high-Ca clinopyroxene lamellae ($Wo_{44.23}En_{34.98}Fs_{20.78}$), a transitional zone ($Wo_{9.01}En_{43.19}Fs_{47.81}$), and a low-Ca orthopyroxene host ($Wo_{3.02}En_{48.11}Fs_{48.87}$) (Fig. 2).

EBSD data further show that the lamellae are crystallographically controlled and that the crystal was later overprinted by fractures (Fig. 3), low-band-contrast seams, and localized increases in misorientation, recording a multistage history of magmatic crystallization, subsolidus exsolution, and later shock-related modification.

Fig. 3 EBSD evidence for crystallographically controlled exsolution lamellae and later fracture-related overprinting in the pyroxene megacryst.

Using the observed lamella width (~40 μm) and pyroxene diffusion modeling, we estimate a cooling rate of $\sim 1.05 \times 10^{-5} \text{ }^\circ\text{C yr}^{-1}$, corresponding to a diffusion timescale of $\sim 3.8 \times 10^7 \text{ yr}$ near a closure temperature of $\sim 700 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. Thermal modeling converts this cooling history to a burial depth of $\sim 23\text{--}32 \text{ km}$, with a preferred estimate of $\sim 28 \text{ km}$, implying derivation from the deep lunar crust [2,3].

Discussion: The coarse pyroxene exsolution lamellae and extremely slow cooling rate indicate prolonged subsolidus cooling in a thermally buffered deep-crustal environment rather than near-surface crystallization. The inferred burial depth suggests that NWA 14685 preserves a rare quantitative record of lower-crustal thermal evolution. Compared with the

nonmare clasts in Chang'e-6 soil, which include noritic anorthosite and norite derived from farside deep crustal levels [4,6], NWA 14685 records a markedly slower and more deeply buffered cooling history and therefore may represent a more deeply buried thermal endmember of the same broad farside deep-crustal system. Comparison with evolved lunar meteorites such as Arguin 002 further suggests that deep-seated lunar noritic/mafic rocks are not necessarily primitive Mg-rich cumulates, but may also include compositionally evolved, KREEP-poor plutonic components [5]. Taken together, these observations suggest that the lower lunar crust was not a simple frozen residue of primary magma-ocean stratification, but a lithologically and thermally heterogeneous domain that underwent post-magma-ocean plutonic reworking, prolonged deep-crustal cooling, and later basin-scale impact excavation [1,5,6].

Conclusion: NWA 14685 preserves a pyroxene megacryst that records crystallization, subsolidus exsolution, and later shock overprinting in a single crystal. Diffusion and thermal modeling indicate extremely slow cooling at depth within the lunar crust, with a preferred burial depth of ~28 km. In combination with recent evidence from Chang'e-6 samples and evolved lunar noritic meteorites [5,6], NWA 14685 provides direct microstructural evidence that the lower lunar crust contained deeply buried, slowly cooled, and lithologically diverse plutonic components.

Acknowledgments: This study was supported by the National Natural Science Foundation of China (No. 42441802), the Scientific Research Innovation Capability Support Project for Young Faculty (No. ZYGXQNJSKYCXNLZCXM-P6), and the Science and Technology Development Fund of Macau (Grants 0052/2024/RIA1).

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